

SCHOOL HEAD'S TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP STYLE AND THE TEACHERS' PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

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School Head's Transformational Leadership Style and the Teachers' Psychological Well-Being

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the influence of school head's transformational leadership style to teachers' psychological well-being. Results show that school head manifests high extent of transformational leadership style; teachers' psychological well-being was also high; school head's transformational leadership significantly influenced teachers' psychological well-being. It was recommended that the school head should continuously stimulate, inspire, and motivate teachers to sustain their psychological well-being and teachers should develop independence and resiliency in their work so that without school head's stimulation and motivation they can still sustain and escalate performance. Lastly, a pragmatic investigation on specific components of transformational leadership style should also be conducted in order to ascertain which specific component singly or collectively influenced teachers' psychological well-being.

Keywords: *school head's transformational leadership style, psychological well-being, organizational success and performance*

Introduction

School administrators are mandated to propel professional development among teachers to improve teaching which benefit the learning population. As school leaders, they are enthused to collaborate with the DepEd to push its recent agenda on teachers' performance in line with the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum to be resilient on its institutional thrusts to sustain quality and globally competitive education through quality teachers and teaching. This requires transformational leadership of the school administrators or school principal.

The framework of this study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to section 4 of rule 3 (Duties and Obligations of the School Heads) of the Education Act of 1982 which mandates that "the school head or school principals shall perform their duties to the school by discharging their responsibilities in accordance with the philosophy, goals, and objectives of the school and develop as well as maintain a healthy school atmosphere conducive to harmonious and progressive school-personnel relationships, and to the promotion and preservation of academic freedom and effective teaching-learning, assume and maintain professionalism in the exercise of their leadership in their work and in their dealings with students, teachers, academic non-teaching personnel, administrative staff, and parents or guardians".

School leaders who provide motivational care and causes change in individuals and social systems create valuable and positive change among teachers and promote health and psychological well-being and become more proficient teachers.

Reyes (2018) reported that transformational leadership has the characteristics that followers attribute to the leader, as well as behavior the leader engages in related to being a role model and doing the right thing. A leader with strong values, who also acts in accordance with these would score highly on this dimensions such charisma or idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and; individualized consideration.

In a similar investigation, Uysal, et al (2018) found out that school administrators who utilized the transformational leadership style do not develop negative relationship and reduced emotional exhaustion and depersonalization of teachers. This means that teachers whose school administrators were transformational leaders were free from any psychological burnout or emotional exhaustion as well as reduced job functions.

Further, transformational school leaders are mentors who can be reassuring of teachers' individual success through coaching and mentoring functions to minimize if not eliminate work-related stress and work burnout.

Avolio (2015) espoused that transformational leadership certainly dominates the leadership landscape. It was found that transformational leaders help enhance employees' psychological well-being through coaching, communicating positive vision, holding high expectations, and intellectual stimulation.

Subsequently, it was also argued that transformational leaders are open to new ways of accomplishing tasks and encouraging others to be creative in their thinking and treat employees as individuals, spend time coaching and developing their skills, cares and are compassionate.

Considering all the characteristics and attributes of the transformational leaders, it was philosophized that this type of school leadership profoundly considers the well-being of its teachers. Teachers' well-being has been conceptualized as including both physical and psychological well-being and health or as job satisfaction.

Consequently, Randall, et al (2018) stipulated the importance of transformational leaders' impact on psychological well-being of the followers. End results of this interaction included followers understanding the importance of their jobs and developing more successful work habits. However, attention should be noted of the impact experienced by the followers of leaders undergoing a change of transformational behaviors.

Additionally, it was concluded that school head transformational leadership created positive psychological well-being to the teachers. The researchers reported followers experienced psychological well-being when the vision and mission were connected to positive self-concepts.

Disputably, school leaders who are transformational leaders provided instructional, administrative, and technical scaffolding to teachers in order to ensure of their psychological well-being so that they can be more proficient in their instructional or teaching functions.

The main concept of this study is premise on the notion that school principals' leadership styles will help improve teachers' performance most particularly in strategic planning which include the preparation of lesson log of activities in all learning areas, preparation and production of appropriate, adequate, and updated instructional materials throughout the school year and in initiating students' discipline including classroom rules, guidelines, individual and group tasks as well as in monitoring students' attendance and the provision of safe and positive learning environments.

It is based on this consideration that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to ascertain whether school head's transformational leadership style and practices positively impact teachers' psychological well-being and health which will also affect their teaching performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to ascertain the Influence of Transformational Leadership Style of School Head to the Psychological Well-being of Teachers of City Central School, Division of Cagayan de Oro City for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the Transformational Leadership Style of the School head of City Central School in the Division of Cagayan City?
2. What is the Level of the Psychological Well-Being of teachers in the Division of Gingoog City?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Level of the Psychological Well-Being of teachers and the Extent of Transformational Leadership Styles of the School Administrators in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilizes the descriptive correlational- research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the school head and teachers of City Central School in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City. There are forty-five (45) public school teachers who were the subject-respondents of the study. They answered the survey questionnaire on the transformational leadership style of the school administrators and the psychological well-being. Subsequently, the respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire adapted from Salem (2019) who conducted a study on the transformational leadership of school administrators and teachers' psychological well-being and teaching performance. The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component is on the school heads' transformational leadership practices with ten (10) indicators while the second part is on the teachers' psychological well-being.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate

School and School Principal to conduct the study.

Subsequently, the researcher administered the research instrument to the teacher-respondents and after they provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the extent of the transformational leadership style of the school heads.

Problem 2. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the level of psychological well-being of the teacher-respondents.

Problem 3. Pearson - Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of psychological well-being and the extent of the transformational leadership style of the school heads in select district of the Division of Cagayan de Oro City.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on school heads' transformational leadership style and the teachers' psychological well-being. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire based on the problems presented.

Problem 1: What is the Transformational Leadership Style of School Head of City Central School of the Division of Cagayan de Oro City?

Table 1. Mean Distribution of the Transformational Leadership Style of School Head

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) School head prioritizes on the Professional development of Teachers.	3.91	1.00	High Extent
2.) School head creates a positive & supportive culture in school.	4.00	.933	High Extent
3.) School head provides support & encourage teachers to enhance Teaching.	4.12	.792	High Extent
4.) School head mediates conflict & introduce the win-win solutions.	4.17	.788	High Extent
5.) School head involves teachers in Implementation of organizational plan.	4.19	.745	High Extent
6.) School head shows teachers how Work was done and led by example.	4.17	.736	High Extent
7.) School head motivates teachers Through rewards.	4.13	.783	High Extent
8.) School head sets standards and is Result-oriented.	4.13	.808	High Extent
9.) School head influences teachers to Achieve outstanding performance.	4.12	.828	High Extent
10.) School head delegates Responsibilities to teachers.	4.12	.828	High Extent
Overall Mean	4.11	.824	High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Extremely High/3.41-4.20 High/2.62-3.40 Moderate/1.81-2.60 Low/1.00-1.80 Extremely Low

Table 1 displays the mean distribution on the school head's transformational leadership style. Overall, the respondents rated the transformational leadership style as "High Extent" with a mean of 4.11 (SD=.824). This result implies that school head had extremely practiced transformational leadership in leading the school and its teachers. It can also be deduced based on findings that school head encourages and inspires teachers to innovate and develop new ways to grow and improve the path in teaching.

The indicator which states that "school head involves teachers in the implementation of organizational plan" obtained the highest mean of 4.19 (SD=.745) which is verbally described as "High Extent". The result indicates that school head provides opportunities for teachers to participate not only in crafting but also in the implementation of the school's development and organizational plan. It can be inferred based on finding that the school head does not only lead the school organization but also empower teachers to take the role leadership in the implementation of school program.

Kendra and Gans (2023) averred that involving teachers in the implementation of school programs is a transformational approach in school leadership. It encourages and inspires teachers to successfully implement the school programs and innovate as well as develop

new ways to grow and improve the path of school future success. Additionally, it was emphasized that using this approach, school heads give trusted teachers the independence to make decisions and support new problem-solving approaches.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.12 (SD=.828) is verbally described as “High Extent” in the indicators “school head influences teachers to achieve outstanding performance” and “school head delegates responsibilities to teachers”. The results imply that the school head inspire teachers to achieve and maintain their exemplary performance and delegate some responsibilities to train teachers assume leadership roles. It can be inferred based on findings that the school head helps develop teachers’ leadership potentials through stimulating teachers to forge higher performance and to assume greater and challenging responsibilities and duties in school.

These findings were supported by Kendra, et al (2023) who emphasized that transformational school head knows how to delegate tasks, duties, and responsibilities to teachers to develop their leadership potentials and skills.

Problem 2: What is the level of the Psychological Well-Being of teachers in the Division of Gingoog City?

Table 2. Mean Distribution of Teachers’ Psychological Well-Being

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Motivated due to school head’s Supportive attitude.	3.87	.950	High Extent
2.) Inspired emotionally by the physical Presence of the school head.	3.90	.906	High Extent
3.) Secured emotionally by the school Head’s support.	3.94	.865	High Extent
4.) Effortlessly adjusts to other Assignments given by the School head.	4.02	.826	High Extent
5.) Lower stresses due to school Head’s sphere of support.	4.00	.808	High Extent
6.) Increases work productivity.	4.05	.842	High Extent
7.) Focuses and concentrates On work and other assignments.	4.04	.836	High Extent
8.) Lower emotional exhaustion or Burn-out due to school head’s Encouragements.	4.04	.836	High Extent
9.) Feels treated as human beings & respected by the school head.	4.04	.836	High Extent
10.) Develops feelings of great Personal accomplishments Due to school head’s Positive comments and Praises for work done.	4.06	.786	High Extent
Overall Mean	4.00	.849	High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Extremely High/3.41-4.20 High/2.62-3.40 Moderate/1.81-2.60 Low/1.00-1.80 Extremely low

Table 2 displays the mean distribution on the teachers’ psychological well-being. Overall, the respondents rated their psychological well-being as “High Extent” with a mean of 4.00 (SD=.849). This result implies that teachers had high psychological well-being because of their school head’s support and personal leadership in stimulating teachers to develop their psychological stability and health. It can also be inferred based on findings that teachers’ psychological well-being is the results of school head’s positive influenced to teachers as manifested in their transformational leadership style.

The indicator which states that “develops the feelings of great accomplishments due to school head’s positive comments and praises for work done” obtained the highest mean of 4.06 (SD=.786) which is verbally described as “High Extent”. The result indicates that school head allows the teachers to feel great and higher personal accomplishments in their work from inspiring and positive notes or comments as well as the generous praises for the school head for the work done or accomplished. It can be deduced based on findings that school head’s constant appreciation to teachers’ accomplishments help contribute enhance their psychological health or well-being.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.87 (SD=.950) is verbally described as “High Extent” in the indicator “motivated due to school head’s supportive attitude”. The result indicates that school head’s sympathetic and reassuring attitude help contribute to teachers’ motivation and increase productivity. It can be inferred based on findings that the teachers’ motivation to succeed in their work and perform better in school is the influenced of school head’s transformational leadership skills.

The findings were supported by Khan (2020) who espoused that transformational school head motivates and stimulates teachers to perform better in their work and achieve anticipated or significant outcomes. It gives teachers self-confidence over specific challenging academic tasks as well as the power to make decisions once they have been trained after delegating some responsibilities.

Additionally, it was also emphasized that school head’s transformational leadership style influenced teachers’ attitude towards job and

behavior. It transforms teachers to become more motivated in their work, inspires them to do better and go beyond what is expected, builds trust, encourages them, admires their innovative ideas, and develops their leadership potentials.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the level of the Psychological Well-Being of teachers and the Extent of Transformational Leadership Style of School Head in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City?

Table 3. *Significant Relationship between Teachers' Psychological Well-Being and School Head's Transformational Leadership*

Leadership Style	Teachers' Psychological Well-Being			
	(rs)	P-Value 2-tailed	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
Transformational Leadership Style	.534	.029	Shows slight Correlation	Rejected

**significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level*

Table 3 displays the results of the test of significant relationship between the level of teachers' psychological well-being and school head's transformational leadership style. Results revealed that school head's transformational leadership shows slight correlation to teachers' psychological well-being as evident by the rs value of .534 which is greater than the p-value of .029. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

This result indicates that school head's transformational leadership style significantly affect teachers' psychological well-being. It can be inferred based on findings that school head who are supportive to the psychological needs of teachers such as inspiring, motivating, and understanding their individual personal needs can stimulate psychological wellness and health among teachers within their school.

Khan (2020) has pointed out that transformational leadership style of school head has a massive and steady influence on teachers' psychological well-being which positively improve job performance and satisfaction. It is a process in which the school head raises their teachers' levels of morality and motivation to transform performance and increase organizational commitment, knowledge management practices, morale, teachers empowerment, level of job satisfaction, levels of transformation toward quality and job effectiveness.

Conclusions

From the findings, it was concluded that in general, that school head's transformational leadership style promotes teachers' psychological well-being.

The study also concluded that the school head manifest high acumen of the transformational leadership which provide extensive support to teachers' personal and professional development. It was inferred that school head's transformational leadership style enhance teachers' psychological well-being.

Additionally, teachers' psychological well-being is enhanced through school head's support in their personal and professional activities. School head's compassion, understanding, immense support to teachers' professional growth, respect, and recognition intensify teachers' psychological health and well-being.

Subsequently, it can be clinched further that school head's transformational leadership style influenced teachers' psychological well-being. This implies that school head's ability to provide support to teachers in their work, the recognition and respect extended as well as teachers' empowerment intensify teachers' psychological health and well-being.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations were being offered to be considered:

School heads are stimulated to continuously practice transformational leadership style in order to unceasingly enhance teachers' psychological well-being in order to sustain organizational commitment, satisfaction, and performance.

Teachers are encouraged to unleash their instructional leadership potentials and develop resiliency in their work challenges. This means that even without recognition from work done from the school head, they can still escalate performance and manifest psychological maturity.

A pragmatic exploration on the components of transformational leadership styles of school head should also be conducted in order to ascertain which specific components singly or collectively influenced teachers' psychological well-being in order to enrich this investigation.

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